

NITROSAMINE IMPURITIES IN PHARMACUTICAL**Miss. Janvi Rajeshwar Umap*, Associate Prof. Ruchika Gawande, Dr. Rahul Bijwar**

Jagadambha Institute of Pharmacy and Research, Kalamb.

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Corresponding Author*Miss. Janvi Rajeshwar Umap**Jagadambha Institute Of Pharmacy
And Research, Kalamb.

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ABSTRACT

N-Nitrosamines (Or Nitrosamines) Are Probable Or Possible Human Carcinogens To Which Can Be Exposed From Several Known Sources, Such As Food, Drinking Water, Tobacco Smoke And Cosmetic Products. However, Until Mid-2018 Their Presence In Medicinal Products Was Unexpected. These Impurities Were First Detected In The Valsartan Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) And Subsequently Other Sartan Medicines Were Also 3implicated. Meanwhile, These Impurities Have Also Been Detected In A Few Non-Sartan Apis And/Or Medicinal Products. The Presence Of N-Nitroso Compounds, Particularly N-Nitrosamines, In Pharmaceutical Products Has Raised Global Safety Concerns Due To Their Significant Genotoxic And Mutagenic Effects. The Regulatory Response To The Nitrosamines Issue Included A Request To All

Marketing Authorization Holders (Mahs) For Human Medicinal Products Containing Chemically Synthesised Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients To Evaluate The Risk Of Nitrosamines Being Present In Their Products And To Take Appropriate Risk Mitigation Measures.

KEYWORDS: Nitrosamine Impurities, Mutagenicity, Carcinogenicity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nitrosamine impurities, even in trace amounts, are highly toxic and mutagenic, capable of damaging DNA, and subsequently in crease the risk of cancer incidence.^[1] Regulatory authorities have identified nitrosamine impurities in various active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) and other approved medications leading to the abrupt recall of drugs like

sartans (valsartan), ranitidine (Zantac), nizatidine, metformin, and varenicline due to unacceptable levels of nitrosamine impurities.^[2]

Nitrosamine impurities are classified as Class 1 known mutagenic impurities according to The International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH) M7 guidelines.^[3] The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) categorized these impurities into Groups 2A and 2B based on epidemiological data. The chemical structures of selected nitrosamines and NDSRIs are represented in Fig. 1.^[4]

To address the nitrosamine crisis, the United States Pharmacopeia (USP) is hosting a virtual platform called the “nitrosamines exchange”. This platform brings together pharmaceutical companies, contract research organizations (CROs), API manufacturers, and excipients suppliers to facilitate real-time communications, updates, and risk assessments related to the nitrosamines issue. Additionally, USP has established a “nitrosamine analytical hub” to provide updates on novel analytical methods for testing nitrosamines. Regulatory authorities for drug control have specified acceptable daily intake limits for various nitrosamine impurities and NDSRIs in APIs and medicinal products. For instance these limits include 96 ng/day for N-nitroso dimethylamine (NMDA) and N-nitroso-N-methyl-4-aminobutanoic acid (NMBA), 26.5 ng/day for N-nitrosomethylphenylamine (NMPA), N-nitrosodiisopropylamine (NDIPA), N-nitrosoisopropylethyl amine (NIPEA), N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDEA), and 1-methyl-4-nitrosopiperazine (MeNP), 34.3 ng/day for NMPA, 37 ng/day for NNV, and 127 ng/day for N-nitrosomorpholine (NMOR). These limits are represented in Fig.2.^[5,6,7]

Fig. No. 01: Chemical structures of various nitrosamine impurities and nitrosamine drug substance-related impurities (NDSRIs).

Fig. No. 2: Acceptable daily intake limits for selected nitrosamines impurities and nitrosamine drug substance-related impurities (NDSRI) in medicinal products as per regulatory authorities.

Ever since the first report of N-nitrosamine impurities in drug products containing the angiotensin II receptor blocker valsartan in 2018, various batches of marketed metformin, ranitidine and varenicline have followed suit.^[8] N-nitrosamines are chemical compounds with a functional N-nitroso group (>N NHO), typically derived from secondary or tertiary amines in the presence of nitrosating agents. They are considered a “cohort of concern” by the International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH) M7, due to their probable or possible human carcinogenic potential.^[9]

1.1 N-nitrosamines Impacting Drug Interaction Studies

In a clinical setting, the concomitant intake of two or more drugs by patients can lead to DDIs that may compromise patient safety or interfere with drug effects. For instance, drugs inhibiting or inducing CYP liver enzymes or inhibiting drug transporter molecules may alter the uptake or clearance of other drugs and potentially lead to supra or sub-therapeutic levels of victim drugs. To avoid unanticipated safety risks, the ICH- issued a guideline requiring that clinically relevant DDIs between investigational drugs and other drugs be assessed during the development of such new drugs.^[10] Development of investigational drugs, especially small molecules, typically includes studies to assess the potential susceptibility of a new drug to pharmacokinetic (PK) interactions that are based on the metabolic pathway of an investigational drug or its suspected influence on key enzyme and transporters.^[11,12]

An example of a DDI drug impacted by N-nitrosamine impurity is ranitidine, a histamine-2 (H₂) blocker used to suppress gastric acid secretions, it was removed from the market in 2019 due to N-nitroso dimethylamine (NDMA) impurities (Table 1). Before this, it was commonly applied as an acid reducing agent in DDI studies for drugs in development at risk of pH-dependant PK changes. Another H₂ blocker, nizatidine, was also recalled due to

similar impurity concerns. Therefore, alternative acid reducing agents should be used in DDI studies, for instance the H-2 blocker famotidine or, as a worst-case scenario design, a proton pump inhibitor such as esomeprazole or rabeprazole can be administered.^[11,12]

In late 2019, the FDA was made aware that batches of metformin, a type 2 diabetes medication, manufactured outside of the US were found to contain NDMA. Upon further testing, it was determined that the extended-release (ER) formulation of the drug was affected, which was subsequently recalled from the American market due to this impurity.^[13] However, the immediate-release (IR) formulation remains free of nitrosamines and is still available for patients. This version of the drug is also used as a substrate of drug transporters (e. g. OCT2 and MATE1/2K) in DDI studies and, therefore, while the observation of N-nitrosamines in ER-metformin has impacted patients, there has been no change in this respect for drug developers (table1).^[14,15]

Recent N-nitrosamine impurity findings can be attributed to closer monitoring of drug products after EMA and FDA issued guidance for industry to control the presence of N-nitrosamine impurities in human drugs in 2020 and 2021, respectively.^[14,15] For instance, N-nitrosamine impurities have been identified in rifampin and rifapentine, which are key antibacterial drugs for the treatment and prevention of tuberculosis (TB), a life-threatening infectious disease. Specifically, 1-methyl-4-nitrospiperazine (MNP) and 1-cyclopentyl 4-nitrosopiperazine (CPNP) were found to be above the acceptable intake (AI) limit in rifampin and rifapentine batches, respectively. Consequently, in addition to negatively impacting the supply of TB treatment, the presence of N-nitrosamines in rifampin batches has also greatly affected clinical drug development. Rifampin is one of the perpetrator drugs commonly employed in clinical DDI studies as a strong clinical index inducer of several key liver enzymes, such as CYP3A4, a potent inducer of the efflux transporter P-glycoprotein as well as an inhibitor of the organic anion transporting polypeptide (OATP)1B1/3^[16] (see Table 1). Prior to contamination concerns, rifampin had an excellent safety profile and was generally well tolerated, even at regimens higher than the common daily dose of 600 mg.^[17] The only exception is that elevations in liver function tests have occasionally been reported in DDI studies, yet these can primarily be attributed to increased concentrations of victim drug metabolites as a result of CYP enzyme induction^[18] and are assumedly not unique for rifampin as an inducer. Due to MNP exceeding the AI limit, regulatory agencies have halted the use of rifampin in healthy volunteer DDI studies and encourage drug developers to

engage alternative perpetrators. A full review of the application of rifampin in DDIs studies, the root cause of MNP in rifampin and alternative CYP3A4 inducers for DDI studies is described here after. Taged End Taged P.^[19]

With such emphasis on nitrosamine control in drug products, a recent in silico analysis revealed that several DDI inhibitors and substrates are potential N-nitrosamine precursors due to their pharmacophore structure and thus likely candidates for NDSRI formation.^[20] While impurities have not been found or confirmed in these compounds, Table 1 provides some examples of these potential NDSRIs related to drugs utilized in DDI studies along with alternative substrates /inhibitors. Of note, the potential nitrosamine risk from secondary amines is greater than that from tertiary amines, as the reaction rate of tertiary amines to form nitrosamines (nitrosative cleavage) is orders of magnitude lower.^[21]

Table 1: DDI Substrates and Inhibitors Impacted by or at Risk of N-nitrosamine Contaminations.

Perpetrator, Drug Class	Role in DDI Studies	N-nitrosamine Impurity	Impact to DDI Studies	Alternatives for DDI Studies
Perpetrator drugs with confirmed N-nitrosamine Impurities				
Ranitidine	Acid reducing agent	NDMA	Product removed from the market in 2019, use alternatives	Famotidine or study with proton pump inhibitor (esomeprazole or abeprazole)
<i>Histamine-2 blocker</i>				
Nizatidine	Acid reducing agent	NDMA	Product recalled in 2020, use alternatives	Famotidine or study with proton pump inhibitor (esomeprazole or abeprazole)
<i>Histamine-2 blocker</i>				
Metformin	OCT2, MATE1/2K substrate	NDMA (ER-metformin only)	No impact	IR-metformin is available for DDI studies and does not contain impurity
<i>Anti-hyperglycaemic agent</i>				
Rifampin	Strong CYP3A4 OATP1B1/3 inhibitor (single dose)	MNP	Batches available for patients only, use alternatives	1. Carbamazepine, efavirenz, lumacaftor, phenytoin 2. Atazanavir & ritonavir, clarithromycin, cyclosporin, gemfibrozil,
<i>Anti-infective agent</i>				

				lopinavir, ritonavir,
Propranolol			Product recalled by Health Canada in 20,227, consider alternatives	
<i>Beta-blocker</i>	Moderate CYP2D6 sensitive substrate	Nitroso-propranolol		Encainide, propafenone
Examples of perpetrator drugs at potential risk of NDSRI				
Clopidogrel				
<i>Antiplatelet</i>	Moderate CYP2C8 index inhibitor	Risk due to tertiary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Gemfibrozil (strong index inhibitor)
Metoprolol				
<i>Beta-blocker</i>	Moderate CYP2D6 sensitive substrate	Risk due to secondary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Encainide, Propafenone
Fluoxetine, Paroxetine				
<i>Antidepressant</i>	Strong CYP2D6 index inhibitors Strong CYP2C19 inhibitor (fluoxetine only)	Risk due to secondary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Mirabegron (moderate inhibitor) Fluconazole
Duloxetine				
<i>Antidepressant</i>	Sensitive CYP1A2 substrate Moderate CYP2D6 inhibitor	Risk due to secondary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Alosetron, Caffeine, Melatonin, Ramelteon, Tasimelteon, Tizanidine Mirabegron
Desipramine				
<i>Antidepressant</i>	Sensitive CYP2D6 index substrate	Risk due to tertiary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Dextromethorphan, Nebivolol
Imipramine				
<i>Antidepressant</i>	Moderate CYP2D6 sensitive substrate	Risk due to tertiary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Encainide, Propafenone
Venlafaxine				
<i>Antidepressant</i>	R-venlafaxine sensitive CYP2D6 substrate S-venlafaxine moderate sensitive CYP2D6 substrate	Risk due to tertiary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Dextromethorphan
Ticlopidine				
<i>Antiplatelet</i>	Strong CYP2C19 inhibitor	Risk due to tertiary amine	Minimal, alternative use optional	Fluconazole

1.2 N-nitrosamines and Cancer Risk

N-nitrosamines are not restricted to drug products and can be found in drinking water, processed foods, cured meats, fish and tobacco smoke.^[22] On average, daily dietary and environmental exposure to N-nitrosamine is estimated at 1.9 – 25.0 mg/day. This exposure is thought to contribute to approximately 6,000 cancer cases per 1 million people.^[23]

However, N-nitrosamine impurities in medications can further exacerbate this risk. For instance, valsartan prescriptions in the US exceeded 5,000,000 per year between 2013–2018,^[24] and the estimated cancer risk associated with valsartan drug products contaminated by N-nitrosamine impurities ranges from 12–126 additional cancer cases per 100,000 exposed individuals.^[25] Specifically, valsartan N-nitrosamine impurities were found to be associated with a slightly increased incidence of hepatic, colorectal and uterine cancer.^[26,27] Although rifampin prescriptions are substantially less, with an estimated 6,000 patients in the US treated with rifampin as part of a 4- or 6-month TB regimen therapy in 2020,^[28] the putative risk of exposure due to N-nitrosamines impurities following rifampin intake is still considerable.^[28]

1.3 The Root Cause and Consequences of MNP in Rifampin

Rifampin is a semi-synthetic drug derived from *Amycolatopsis mediterranea*, which naturally produces the antibiotic rifamycin B (reviewed in Wohlfart *et al.*).^[29] During the last step of the synthesis process, conversion with 1-amino-4-methyl piperazine (AMP) results in the formation of rifampin. However, it should be noted that AMP is a precursor for MNP (Fig. 3) and it is thought that AMP reacts with free nitrites (hydrolysed from alkyl nitrites during the reaction) or can be oxidized by aerial oxygen to form MNP,^[29] thus contaminating batches of rifampin. Another potential source of MNP in rifampin is through thermal degradation. Tao and colleagues demonstrated that MNP levels can increase by 25% when stored at 40 °C, and levels even double when stored at 60 °C.^[30]

Fig. No. 03: Formation of MNP during the synthesis of rifampicin.

2. HISTORY

1950s–1960s: Carcinogenicity Identified

- Researchers established that nitrosamines cause cancer in laboratory animals.
- They were initially identified as potential carcinogens.

1970s: Detection in Food and Beverages

- Nitrosamines were found in beverages, preserved foods, and other products.
- Studies linked the use of sodium nitrate as a preservative in fish to nitrosamine generation and carcinogenicity.

2018: Nitrosamine Discovery in Pharmaceuticals

- **June 2018:** The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) discovered NDMA, a nitrosamine, in batches of the blood pressure medication valsartan.
- **July 2018:** The European Medicines Agency (EMA) also reported finding NDMA and N-nitrosodiethylamine (NDEA) in other "sartan" drugs.

2019: Ranitidine and Metformin Contamination

- Further testing revealed unacceptable levels of NDMA in ranitidine (heartburn medication).
- NDMA was also found in metformin, an anti-diabetic drug.
- The World Health Organization (WHO) released a key information note on nitrosamine impurities in November 2019

2020s: Global Regulatory Actions & Expansion of Concerns

- Regulatory agencies worldwide began to issue comprehensive guidance and requests for manufacturers to evaluate the risk of nitrosamine impurities in their products.
- More nitrosamines, such as N-nitrosodiisopropylamine (NDIPA) and N-nitrosoethylisopropylamine (NEIPA), were identified in various drug classes.
- Regulatory focus expanded to cover a wider range of medicines, including sitagliptin, quinapril, fluoxetine, and duloxetine, leading to ongoing recalls and risk assessments.

3. SOURCES OF NITROSAMINE

There are many ways that people might be exposed to nitrosamines, including through drinking water, food, tobacco, personal care items, rubber goods, pesticides and industrial

exposure. The second biggest source of nitrosamine exposure, after cigarettes, has been found as nitrosamine absorption through food intake, regardless of dietary preferences.^[31,32]

The potential sources of Nitrosamine are described in Figure 4.^[33,34] The production of nitrosamines as contaminants in pharmaceutical medicines can be caused by a number of methods.^[33,34]

Fig. No. 04: The potential sources of Nitrosamines.

4. Molecular Toxicity of Nitrosamine Impurities

NDMA, NDEA, N-nitrosoethylisopropylamine (NEIPA), NDIPA, N nitrosodibutylamine (NDBA), and NMBA are the predominant nitrosamines that can foster the carcinogenic effects via genotoxicity or mutagenicity in the physiological system. In recent years, it has become evident that impurities in several pharmaceutical products pose significant human health risks, as observed in rodent models. For example, NMBA and NDEA have metabolic similarities to the NMDA and 12 carcinogenic N-nitroso methyl-N-alkylamines (NMAs). Both genotoxicity and tumorigenicity are assessed through the examination of chromosomal aberrations, sister chromatid ex. Change, and micronuclei formation during studies on nitrosamines induced toxicity studies.^[35-40]

4.1 Genotoxicity

Nitrosamine impurities such as NDMA, NDEA, and others can induce mutagenic effects and subsequently thereby leading to carcinogenicity. NDMA has been shown to induce mutations due to the genotoxicity in vivo models.^[35-40] Cytochrome P450 (CYP450) enzymes such as CYP2E1 and CYP2A6 are involved in the metabolism of N-nitrosamines and form N-nitroso dialkylamines.^[41-43] For instance, in rodent models, CYP2E1 is implicated in the metabolism of several substrates including organic solvents, nitrosamines, and other drug molecules.^[44] Additionally, CYP3A4 plays a role in catalyzing the activation of larger N-nitrosamines.^[45] The differential expression of CYP2E1 modulates the nitrosamines metabolism in different in vitro or in vivo models.^[46,47]

Genotoxicity of 4-(methylnitrosamine)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butane (NNK)-mediated DNA damage includes the formation of methyl DNA base adducts, such as O6-Me-dGuo and N7-Me-dGuo. Other genotoxic products resulting from the activity of N-nitrosamines in the healthy cells include methyl DNA base adducts and pyridyloxobutyl (POB) DNA base adducts including O6-POB-dGuo, and O2-POB-Thd. Aldehyde DNA adducts are also significant genotoxic products formed due to the presence of nitrosamine impurities.^[48,49]

4.2 Carcinogenicity

Several epidemiological reports have described the influence of nitrosamines on the risk of developing esophageal cancers, colon cancers, hepatocellular cancers, and other devastating forms of cancers.^[50-52]

4.2.1 Lung cancer

Lung cancer can be induced by the nitrosamine impurities, as they have the ability to stimulate proliferation, migration, and cancer cell survival by modulating G-protein signaling, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) signaling, and epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) signaling. For instance, nitrosamines' influence on EGFR signaling can induce changes in the cyclic adenosine monophosphate-protein kinase A-rapidly accelerated fibrosarcoma-mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase-extracellular signal regulated kinase 1/2 (cAMP-PKA-RAF-MEK-ERK1/2) axis, subsequently promoting cancer cell proliferation. Similarly, the EGFR modulation could cause alterations in the phosphoinositide-3 kinase-Akt-mammalian target of rapamycin (PI3K-Akt-Mtor) signaling pathway to fostering cancer cell survival. Nitrosamines also induce changes in nAChR signaling, voltage gated calcium channel (VGCC), calcium signaling, and protein kinase C

(PKC) modulation, which contribute to cancer progression through migration and survival. HIF1-alpha signaling is also modulated by the beta-adrenergic signaling when nitrosamines interact with these receptors which subsequently cause angiogenesis for nutrient supply to the proliferating cancer cells.^[53]

4.2.2. Esophageal cancer

Esophageal cancer has higher incidence rates and wide geographical prevalence, indicating the involvement of environmental factors in its development. Past reports in toxicogenomics have described the role of nitrosamines. Esophageal cancer has higher incidence rates and wide geographical prevalence in esophageal carcinogenesis. A study by Zhao *et al.* elucidated the potential of nitrosamine to induce carcinogenicity in the esophageal epithelium.^[53]

In this study, the authors examined the urinary levels of nitrosamines in patients associated with esophageal squamous cell carcinoma (ESCC), basal cell hyperplasia, and precancerous lesions, comparing them to healthy individuals.^[53]

4.2.3. Hepatocellular and pancreatic cancer

Hepatocellular cancer is one of the lethal cancers that can result from the metabolism of nitrosamines with the involvement of P450 enzymes. Lifestyle factors, such as dietary exposure to higher levels of nitrosamines or N-nitroso compounds, have been linked to the development of cancer.^[54,55] These compounds specifically form DNA adducts in the nuclei of cells located in digestive organs and the liver contributing to the carcinogenicity of nitroso compounds.^[56,57] Furthermore, food processing additives containing these compounds serve as a significant source of nitrosamine exposure in humans.^[58,59]

Dose-response relationships concerning nitrosamines have shown that NDMA and NDEA induce hepatic tumors in *in vivo* models. DNA adduct formation has been observed in both *in vivo* models and human in liver tumors with significant nitrosamines exposure.^[60-65] N-nitrosamines induce the hydroxylation of an alpha-carbon atom within the alkyl group, generating hydroxyl nitrosamines in liver cells and subsequently fostering DNA alkylation. These sequential events further cause gene damage, mutations, and confers malignant transformation of liver cells into cancer cells by triggering oncogenic signalling.^[66-69] as represented in Fig.5. Furthermore, exposure to N-nitrosamines affects hepatic lipid metabolism through alterations in mitochondrial DNA, oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) signaling, and other mitochondrial metabolic pathways. Another mechanism of

nitrosamines involves the induction of inflammation in liver tissue through oxidative stress, adenosine triphosphate (ATP) depletion, and a decline in enzymes related to fatty acid oxidation.^[70]

Table 2: The carcinogenic potential of N-nitroso compounds across various routes of administration in several in vivo models.

The carcinogenic potential of N-nitroso compounds across various routes of administration in several in vivo models.

N-nitroso compounds	No.	Route of administration	Animal models	Tumors
N-nitrosodimethylamine (NMDA)	1	Oral	Mice, rats, hamsters, rabbits, guinea pigs, and fish	Benign and malignant tumors of the liver
	2	Inhalation	Mice, prenatal exposure in mice	Benign and malignant tumors of the liver
	3	Subcutaneous	Hamsters, mastomys, and newborn and suckling mice and rats	Benign and malignant tumors of the liver
	4	Intraperitoneal	Adult and newborn mice and in newts	Benign and malignant tumors of the liver
	5	Intramuscular	Rats	Benign and malignant tumors of the liver
	6	Oral	Frogs and fish	Benign and malignant tumors of the liver
	7	Oral	Lung tumors in mice	Tumors of the respiratory tract
	8	Inhalation	Mice and rats	Lung tumors
	9	Inhalation	Rats	Nasal-cavity tumors
	10	Subcutaneous	Adult, newborn, and suckling mice and nasal cavity tumors in adult hamsters	Lung tumors
	11	Intraperitoneal	Adult and newborn mice	Lung tumors
	12	Inhalation	Rats	Nasal-cavity tumors
	13	Inhalation	Mice	Lung tumors
	14	Oral exposure	Mice, rats, and hamsters	Blood-vessel tumors
	15	Subcutaneous	Hamsters and adult, newborn, and suckling mice	Blood-vessel tumors
	16	Intraperitoneal	Mice	Blood-vessel tumors
	17	Oral	Frogs	Tumors of the hematopoietic system
	18	Oral	Mollusks	Tumors of the digestive gland and hematopoietic system
	19	Subcutaneous	Female hamsters	Ovarian tumors
	20	Oral	Foxes	Liver tumors
	21	Intraperitoneal	Rats	Lung and liver tumors
	22	Oral	Humans	Oropharyngeal cancer
	23	Oral		Stomach
	24	Oral		Esophageal
	25	Oral		Colorectal
N-nitrosodiethylamine (NDEA)	1	Inhalation	Rats	Liver tumors
	2	Rectal	Rats	Liver tumors
	3	Intramuscular	Chickens and cats	Liver tumors
	4	Intraperitoneal	Newborn mice	Liver tumors
	5	Intratracheal	Hamsters of both sexes	Tumors of the lung or trachea
	6	Subcutaneous	Rabbits	Tumors of the lung or trachea
	7	Intraperitoneal	Newborn mice	Tumors of the lung or trachea
	8	Oral	Larval or juvenile fish	Pancreatic tumors
	9	Oral	Mollusks	Tumors of the digestive gland and hematopoietic system
	10	Intraperitoneal	Pregnant hamsters, prenatally exposed offspring, and second generation of offspring	Benign laryngotracheal tumors
N-nitrosomorpholine (NMOR)	1	Oral	Male hamsters, female rats, and male hamsters	Respiratory or digestive-tract tumors
	2	Intravesicular	Rats	Tumors of internal organs
	3	Oral	Female rats	Tumors of the esophagus
	4	Oral	Male mice	Hepatocellular adenoma
	5	Oral	Rats	Hepatocellular carcinoma and cholangiofibroma
	6	Intravenous	Rats	Liver cancer
	7	Oral	Syrian golden hamsters	Malignant liver tumors
	8	Oral	Hamsters	Respiratory or digestive-tract tumors
	9	Oral	Hamsters	Tumors of the respiratory tract and upper digestive tract

4.2.4. Breast cancer

Breast cancer remains a major cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide, often attributed to unhealthy life style patterns and dietary habits. Tobacco contains a wide range of nitrosamines, with NNK being a significant carcinogen known to promote the malignant cancer cells.^[71] These tobacco derived carcinogens are particularly relevant to the development of various cancers including breast cancer. NNK plays a significant role in the development and progression of breast cancer by interacting with the nAChR present in cancer cells. Notably, the $\alpha 9$ nAChR receptor is implicate the development and progression of breast cancer cells.^[72,73]

Additionally, nicotine and NNK can interact with this receptor system, subsequently influencing cancer cell proliferation by modulating crucial cell signaling pathways like mitogen activated protein kinase (MAPK) and PI3K-Akt pathways. These signaling pathways are stimulated by the activity of nicotine and estrogen hormone stimulation. The activation of a $\alpha 9$ nAChR by NNK and nicotine forms a significant feedback loop through PI3K-Akt and MAPK signaling, which could further initiate activator protein 1 (AP1) and vitamin D receptor (VDR) transcription factors stimulation to confer to the cancer development.^[74,77] This phenomenon has been confirmed through gene knockdown studies of a $\alpha 9$ nAChR using small interfering RNA (siRNAs).^[78,80]

Fig. No. 05: Molecular signaling pathway for nitrosamines in various types of cancers.

4.3. Physiological alterations: nitrosamine impurities in angiotensin receptor blockers

NDMA, NDEA, NEIPA, NDIPA, NDBA, and NMBA are major nitrosamines known to induce carcinogenicity in the physiological system.^[90] Additionally, these impurities found in pharmaceutical drugs could cause alterations in the physiological system. For instance, angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) such as losartan, valsartan, Olmesartan, irbesartan, and telmisartan have been recalled from US markets due to elevated levels of nitrosamine impurities in their products, which can disrupt physiological homeostasis.^[81] The presence of these nitrosamines in ARBs is primarily attributed to improper manufacturing process.^[82]

DNA adducts such as O6-methylguanine (O6-Me-Gua) and N7 Me-Gua induced by the NDMA when incubated with exophages cell cultures obtained from human tissues.^[83] Methylated DNA adducts observed across the human tissues could typically damage the healthy cells.^[84-86] In case of liver cell DNA, the NDMA poisoned victims, O6-Me-Gua and N7-Me-Gua formation was observed. In case of NMEA, N7-Me-Gua is methylated form of DNA adducts formed substantially in hepatic region and renal region followed by the exophages and lungs. These toxic DNA adducts may further harm the cell protein formation at transcriptional and translational levels which required substantial future studies to unravel the underlying mechanisms behind these N-nitroso compounds-induced physiological alterations.^[87]

5. Discovery of nitrosamines in medicinal products

On 6 June 2018, active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) manufacturer Zhejiang Huahai Pharmaceutical (ZHP) from China detected NDMA contamination in the manufacturing process of valsartan. Investigation showed that nitrosamine contaminants in the ZHP plant appeared after July 2012, when parts of valsartan production changed to increase yields and reduce waste. More specifically, the manufacturer changed the synthetic process involving tetrazole ring formation by replacing tributyltinazide with a more toxic anhydrous sodium azide, while dimethylformamide (DMF) was used as the solvent. Sodium nitrite, which forms nitrous acid in an acidic medium, was used to quench the excess sodium azide, which resulted in the nitrosation of dimethylamine (DMA) impurity present in dimethylformamide to form NDMA (Fig. 6).^[88]

Fig. No. 06: Production changes that caused formation of NDMA in the Zhejiang Huahai Pharmaceutical plan.

6. CONCLUSION

Awareness in the mutagenic and carcinogenic potential has increased in consequence to the latest discovery of Nitrosamine impurities on several commercially available medications. Due to the solvent, catalyst, and raw materials utilized throughout the production process, these impurities developed on the drug product. To manage various nitrosamine impurity, the various regulatory agencies have issued to alter the production process's control procedures, so that these impurities can be avoided.

The presence of MNP in rifampin batches has shifted the risk-benefit ratio for both patients and clinical DDI study participants. While a temporary elevation of the AI limit has been justified to provide patients access to life-saving rifampin treatment, its administration remains prohibited for healthy volunteers in DDI studies that are conducted as part of clinical drug development.

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ABBREVIATION

API: Active pharmaceutical ingredient

AMP: 1-amino-4-methyl piperazine

AI: Acceptable intake

ARB: angiotensin receptor blockers

CROs: contract research organizations

CYP: Cytochrome P450

CPNP: 1-cyclopentyl-4-nitrosopiperazine

CAMP-PKA-RAF-MEK-KRK 1/2: cyclic adenosine monophosphate-protein kinase A-rapidly accelerated fibrosarcoma-mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase-extracellular signal regulated kinase 1/2

DNA: Deoxyribonucleic acid

DDI: Drug-Drug interaction

DMF: dimethylformamide

DMA: dimethylamine

ER: Extended release

EMA: European Medicines Agency

EGFR: Epidermal growth factor receptor

ESCC: Esophageal squamous cell carcinoma

FDA: Food and drug administration

ICH: International council for harmonisation

IARC: International agency for research on cancer

IR: Immediate release

MNP: 1-methyl-4-nitrosopiperazine

MAPK: mitogen activated protein kinase

MAHs: Marketing authorization holders

NDSRIs: Nitrosamine drug substance – related impurities

NMDA: N-nitroso dimethylamine

NMBA: N-Nitroso-N-methyl-4-aminobutyric acid

NMPA: N-Nitrosomethylphenylamine

NDIPA: N-Nitrosodiisopropylamine

NIEPA: N-Nitrosoethylisopropylamine

NDEA: N-Nitrosodiethylamine

NNV: N-nitroso-varenicline

NMOR: N-nitroso morpholine

NDMA: N-nitroso dimethylamine

NMA: N- nitroso methylaniline

NNK: 4-(methyl nitrosamine)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone

nAChR: Nicotinic acetylcholine receptor

OATP: Organic anion transporting polypeptide

POB: P-hydroxybenzoic acid

USP: United states pharmacopeia

VDR: volatility distribution ratio

ZHP: Zhejiang Huahai Pharmaceutical